

Thermoelectric Micro- / Nano - Cementitious Composites For Potential Thermal Energy Harvesting

Ioanna Vareli, A.Gkaravela, E. Tzouma, N.-M. Barkoula, A.S. Paipetis

Motivation

Urban Environment

Infrastructure

- Cost-effective
- Versatile
- Durable
- Constructable
- Available

Motivation

“Infrastructure either directly or indirectly influence all 17 of the SDGs, including 121 of the 169 targets (72%).”

Thacker et al, Nature Sustainability, 2019

Cement industry
(8-10 % of global CO₂ emission)

2020 Global status report for buildings and construction, UN Environment programme, Global Alliance for Buildings and Construction.

Can cement become sustainable by adding new functionalities?

Smart and multi-functional cement

Smart materials: Designed with properties that can be significantly changed in a controlled fashion by external stimuli such as stress, moisture, electric field or magnetic fields.

Basics of Thermoelectricity - State-of-the-Art

The Seebeck Effect (S)

Thermoelectric Power Generation

$$ZT = \frac{S^2 \sigma}{\kappa} T$$

$$PF = S^2 \sigma \text{ (}\mu\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-2}\text{)}$$

$$S = \Delta V / \Delta T \text{ (}\mu\text{V/K)}$$

Ideal Thermoelectric Material

- Higher Seebeck coefficient (S)
- Higher electrical conductivity (σ)
- Lower thermal conductivity (κ)

- Thermoelectric properties for *p*-type cement-based composites with carbon inclusions as found in the literature.

Materials	Concentration (wt.%)	S ($\mu\text{V/K}$)	Ref
Carbon Fibers + MWCNT	0.4 + 0.5	21.7	Zuo et al. 2018
Graphene Nanoplatelets	15.0	340	Ghosh et al. 2019
SWCNT	0.5	1348.8	Vareli et al. 2021
Reduced Graphene Oxide	0.15	159.7	Cui et al. 2022
TZ + nano Fe_2O_3 + CF	0.6 + 0.5+0.5	1123.4	Wan et al. 2023

Micro- and nano- conductive cement-based nanocomposites

- Electrically and Thermoelectrically conductive
- Energy Storage
- Energy Harvesting

Hierarchical – SWCNT/Carbon Fibers (CFs)

Micro- and nano- composites fabrication & characterisation

Electrical conductivity of cement-based micro- and nanocomposites

Cement/micro- and nano-composites

- Examined at: 7, 14 and days
- Higher electrical conductivity ($\sigma = 1.41 \times 10^3 \text{ S/m}$) corresponds to the cement/SWCNT enhanced with 0.5 wt.% SWCNT
- High value compared to the SWCNT inherent electrical conductivity ($\sigma = 10^4 \text{ S/m}$)

Thermoelectric properties (S , PF) of cement/SWCNT-nCB nanocomposites

Cement/micro- and nano-composites

- Seebeck coefficients (S) at 7, 14, 28 days, at the steady state.
 - $S = S_{el} + S_{ionic}$
 - Highest measured S value for cement/SWCNT-nCB (0.5-0.25) = 4644.2 $\mu\text{V/K}$ at $\Delta T = 25 \text{ K}$.
- Energy filtering at the interface of SWCNT-nCB greatly enhance S .
 - Intentionally chosen **low thermal gradients** keeping in mind the potential TE applications.
- The σ , S and $PF = 1.51 \times 10^4 \mu\text{W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-2}$, values reported here are the highest among carbonaceous cement-based composites.

Cement/SWCNT TEG device performance and power output characteristics

Cement/SWCNT TEG device

- 10 cement/ SWCNT (0.5) p-type thermoelements serially interconnected at $\Delta T = 25$ K.
- Experimentally measured R_{TEG} , V_{TEG} (otherwise defined as V_{out} or open circuit voltage V_{oc} of the device) and short circuit current (I_{sc}).
 - Experimentally measured $V_{TEG} = 15.7$ mV
 $(V_{TEG} = V_1 + V_2 + \dots + V_{10})$
 Expected and theoretical $V_{TEG} = N \times S \times \Delta T = 337$ mV
- Cement ions are not harvested to the external circuit at the TEG level; still contribute to charge-transfer doping to the SWCNTs enhancing their p-type character.
- Maximum electrical power output (P_{max})

$$P_{max} = \frac{(N S \Delta T)^2}{4R_0} = \frac{\Delta V^2}{4R_0} \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$
 - Expected $P_{max} = 1.26 \mu\text{W}$ at $\Delta T = 25$ K
Experimentally measured $P_{max} = 579.4 \mu\text{W}$ at $\Delta T = 25$ K

Cement/SWCNT-nCB TEG device performance and power output characteristics

Cement/SWCNT-nCB TEG device

- 10 cement/ SWCNT-nCB (0.5-0.25) p-type thermoelements interconnected in parallel at $\Delta T = 25$ K.
 - Experimentally measured $V_{TEG} = 384.3$ mV
 $(V_{TEG} = V_1 + V_2 + \dots + V_{10})$
 Expected and theoretical $V_{TEG} = N \times S \times \Delta T = 1.85$ V
- Cement ions are not harvested to the external circuit at the TEG level; still contribute to charge-transfer doping to the SWCNTs enhancing their p-type character.
 - Expected $P_{max} = 3.55$ μ W at $\Delta T = 25$ K
Experimentally measured $P_{max} = 0.369$ μ W at $\Delta T = 25$ K

Hybrid-TEG device performance and power output characteristics

Number of TE	Type of TE	TE connection	TEG connection	TEG Power density @ $\Delta T=25K$
10	Cement/ SWCNT	In series	-	1.28 mW/m ² ¹⁹
10	Cement/SWCNT-nCB	In parallel	-	0.36 mW/m² (This work)
20	Cement/SWCNT-nCB & Cement/ SWCNT	-	In parallel	1.20 W/m² (This work)

$R_{TEG} = 1.02 \text{ Ohm}$

$V_{TEG} = 99.32 \text{ mV}$

$I_{SC} = 38.93 \text{ }\mu\text{A}$

Summary – Next Steps

- The **thermoelectric properties** of **cement nanocomposites** with **single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNT)**, **nano-Carbon Black** and **Hierarchical Carbon Fibers** at **28** days of hydration are reported.
- The as-developed thermoelements with inherent **p-type** semiconductor characteristics were introduced into the cementitious matrix as thermoelectric materials for future energy harvesting applications.
- **28** days cement/SWCNT-nCB sample with **0.5 wt.% and 0.25 wt.% loading** exhibited the highest performance in terms of S (+ 4644.2 $\mu\text{V/K}$) and PF ($1.51 \times 10^4 \mu\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-2}$)
- **(i) Cement/SWCNT (0.5) , Cement/SWCNT-nCB(0.5 – 0.25), and Cement/SWCNT-CF** was used for the fabrication of a thermoelectric generator (**TEG**) device exhibiting a maximum **power output** (P_{max}) of 0.789 μW upon being exposed to a temperature difference (ΔT) of 25 K.
- In conclusion, p-type cement/SWCNT-nCB nanocomposites act differently when incorporated into a TEG device.
- Fabrication of p⁺/n⁻ TEG device

Acknowledgements

European Union
European Regional
Development Fund

ΕΡΑνηΕΚ 2014-2020
OPERATIONAL PROGRAMME
COMPETITIVENESS • ENTREPRENEURSHIP • INNOVATION

This research has been co-financed by the European Union and Greek national funds through the Operational Program Competitiveness, Entrepreneurship, and Innovation, under the call RESEARCH-CREATE-INNOVATE (**HICOTEΓ-T1EDK-03482**).

**Thank you for your attention.
Any questions?**

Ioanna Vareli

ivareli@hotmail.com

i.vareli@uoi.gr